

- 1 **Impact of high tidal volume ventilation on surfactant metabolism and lung injury**
- 2 **in infant rats – Supplemental Material**
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5 **Figure S1.**

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7 **Figure S1.** Representative photographs from hematoxylin-eosin (HE) stained lung
8 sections from (A) non-ventilated controls (NVC) and ventilated animals with (B) V_T 8
9 mL/kg and PEEP 5 cmH₂O ($V_{T8PEEP5}$), (C) V_T 16 mL/kg and PEEP 5 cmH₂O
10 ($V_{T16PEEP5}$), (D) V_T 24 mL/kg and PEEP 5 cmH₂O ($V_{T24PEEP5}$), and (E) V_T 24
11 mL/kg and PEEP 1 cmH₂O ($V_{T24PEEP1}$). Note that alveolar edema and hyaline
12 membranes were not present. Alveolar macrophages are indicated by *arrows*. V_T =
13 tidal volume; PEEP = positive end-expiratory pressure. Original magnification $\times 40$, *bar*
14 = 100 μ m.

15 **Figure S2.**

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17 **Figure S2.** Number and relative surface area of alveoli normalized to lung parenchyma
 18 surface area in the study groups. (A) Number of alveoli and (B) surface area of alveoli
 19 were assessed in hematoxylin-eosin (HE) stained lung sections. Data are displayed as
 20 box plots with median, 10th, 25th, 75th, and 90th percentiles. N = 11-13 per treatment
 21 group. * displays a significant difference between NVC versus V_T16PEEP5,
 22 V_T24PEEP5, and V_T24PEEP1, # indicates significant differences between NVC versus
 23 V_T16PEEP5; *, # at the end of the protocol, where p < 0.05. NVC = non-ventilated
 24 control; V_T = tidal volume; PEEP = positive end-expiratory pressure.

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26 **Figure S3.**

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29 **Figure S3.** Representative electron micrographs of (A) a mitotic alveolar epithelial type
30 II (AE2_{mit}) cell and (B) an intermediate alveolar epithelial (AE_{int}) cell. (A) AE2 cell at the
31 end of telophase/beginning of cytokinesis, which can be identified by two nuclei within
32 a cellular body. AE2 cells can be detected by cuboidal shape, rounded nuclei, lamellar
33 bodies (LBs), and apical surface microvilli (*black arrows*). (B) An AE_{int} cell in a closed
34 proximity to two alveolar epithelial type I (AE1) cells. AE1 cells have flattened nuclei,

35 little perinuclear cytoplasm, and long cytoplasmic extensions (*black arrowheads*). AE_{int}
36 cell displays characteristics of both AE2 and AE1 cells with apical microvilli and LBs
37 as well as flattened nuclei and cytoplasmic extensions (*white arrow heads*). Note the
38 covering of a cytoplasmic extension of AE_{int} cell by a very thin cytoplasmic extension
39 of AE1 cell. Original magnification ×2,600.

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